

SECURITY OF LIVES AND PROPERTY: AN APPRAISAL OF ONDO STATE GOVERNMENT DIRECTIVE ON INSTALLATION OF CLOSED-CIRCUIT TELEVISION CAMERA

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Abstract: Insecurity has become a growing concern worldwide. It has become one of the major challenges facing Nigeria. It is a problem that has significantly threatened and undermined the peaceful existence of the country. Governments and organizations globally have been exploring various measures to address this challenge. This paper, therefore appraised Ondo State Government directive on installation of closed-circuit television camera (CCTV). The study used both quantitative and qualitative techniques of research methods to analyse and interpret data collected. Two hundred and six respondents were selected from residents of Owo Local Government Area. Findings of the study revealed low level of awareness on the directive and poor compliance level. This was attributed to the fact that the directive was an executive order rather than a Law. The study therefore recommended passing the directive into a law so as to empower security agents to enforce it legally. Also, the state government should collaborate with civil organizations and non-governmental organizations to create public awareness for the directive. Finally, youth empowerment and employment should be addressed so as to reduce vulnerability of young people to criminal activities.

Keywords: Closed-circuit television camera, Directive, Insecurity, Lives and Property.

1. INTRODUCTION

Over the years, the world has witnessed the increased in the threat to lives and property. The emergence of dreaded terrorist organizations such as Al-Qaeda formed by Osama Bin Laden, Islamic State of Iraq and the Levant (ISIS) formed by Abu Bakral- Baghdadi, Taliban formed by Mullah Muhammad Omar, etc. have caused direct economic destruction of lives and property (Owolabi & Ayenakin, 2015). Africa is not immune from the carnage caused by insecurity. The continent has witnessed the spread of terrorist groups such as Al-Qaeda in the Islamic Maghreb (AQIM), Islamic State (IS) in the greater Sahara, Ansarul Islam, Al-shabaab, and most notorious, Boko Haram (Chatham House, 2021). In recent times, insecurity of lives and property has reached an unprecedented level in Nigeria (Udeoba & Eze, 2021). The county has faced different forms of internal crises, social and political chaos and crimes for decades, but of which recent years has seen the transformation of common hitherto crimes into cattle rustling, banditry, kidnapping, insurgency, e.t.c (Owolabi &

Ayenakin, 2015; Ekoja et al,2022). The insecurity threat in Nigeria includes oil theft, organized armed robbery, kidnapping, assassination, banditry cattle rustling, social injustice and vandalisation of private and public property (Udeoba & Eze, 2021). According to Mahmoud and Madori (2013) every region in Nigeria from the North to the East and to the west is battling with various forms of security challenge ranging from Boko Harm insurgency, kidnapping, armed Banditry, farmers/herders clashes etc.

Insecurity has caused significant damage to lives and property in Nigeria (Mahmoud & Madori, 2013) observed that it has led to a low life expectancy rate, low level in standard education, poor economic growth because of low investment of local and foreign investors. The cases of destruction of lives and property have very negative implications to the Nigeria economic as no foreign investors want to put his money where it is not secured (Udeoba & Eze, 2021). The damaged of existing infrastructure such as the destruction of the United Nations building in Abuja by Boko Haram insurgents, the attacked on the Kuje correctional facilities by elements of ISWAP and the ravaged of communities in the North-east geopolitical Zone, most especially in Borno State, the epicenter of insurgency in Nigeria has prevented development of critical infrastructure and provision of safer environment for the growth of economic activities (Udeoba & Eze, 2021).Despite the huge budgetary allocation to Security agencies by the federal government, and the establishment of various security outfits by state governments, Nigeria is still battling with menace of kidnapping, insurgency, communal clashes and armed robbery (Abullahi, 2022). Government response to further strengthen security agencies and increase their capacities to fight insecurity challenges informed the passage of the 2011 Anti-terrorism Act (Abdullahi, 2022). In spite of government's efforts to tackle insecurity challenges through Anti-terrorism Act, the level of insecurity of lives and property is prevalence and the country has been consistency ranked low in the Global Peace index (GPI, 2012). Adeleke (2013) argues that Nigerian security agencies has been helpless in the face of bombing and killings in the North; kidnapping and robbery attacks in the South, politically and economically related killings, as well communal clashes which have turned into dangerous monster. Abdullahi (2022) argues that state security apparatus saddled with the duties and responsibilities of securing life and property have not performed well in their duties and their inability to effectively police the nation has led to the upsurge of private security outfits. The ineffectiveness of the security agencies in Nigeria was further exposed on June 5, 2022 with the attacked of St. Francis Catholic Church, Owaluwa in Owo, Ondo state by suspected terrorists.

According to Arise News (2022) at least over 50 worshipers were reportedly killed while many sustained various injuries when gunmen invaded the church using explosives and sophisticated weapons. The condemnation that trailed the senseless and barbaric killing of innocent worshippers in Owo, Ondo state and other attacks across Nigeria has become the most discussed issues haunting citizens as to whether security agencies who are grossly underfund and poorly trained in crime, detection and prevention can effectively guarantee the safety of lives and property (Adeleke, 2013). Insecurity has been a major issue in Nigeria and there is no dearth of studies on insecurity challenges in Nigeria. While Ekoja et al (2022) look into entrepreneurial ventures and insecurity in Nigeria, Adeleke (2013) study explains that security is sine qua non for the sound existence of human being, a nation, its Unity and economic prosperity as well as its political stability. Onoja (2014) study observed that political administrator's inability to fulfill electoral campaign promises fueled insecurity while Abdullahi (2022) study concluded that insecurity challenges such as unemployment, terrorism, corruption, religious and ethnic violence has been a major bane to Nigeria's development. Also, Udoh (2015) study looks into insecurity and its implications for political, religious and cultural in Nigeria. The study suggested that if insecurity in Nigeria is not tamed, it is capable of derailing the political and economic development plans of the nation. Despite avalanches of studies on insecurity challenges in Nigeria, a paucity of information exists on how the use of closed-circuit television (CCTV) could assist and complement the efforts of security agencies fight against insecurity challenges. It is based on the foregoing that this study examines insecurity challenges in Nigeria. The main focus of this study is to appraise directive of Ondo state government on installation of closed-circuit television camera (CCTV) using Owo local government area as a case study. The study recommended possible ways to reduce crimes and criminalities in the local government area.

Statement of the Problem

Insecurity challenge is a major bane to the socio-political development in Nigeria. The prevalent insecurity has caused Nigeria and Nigerians enormous human and material resources (Adeleke, 2013). The frequent activities of bandits, Boko Haram insurgency, kidnapping for ransom, herders/farmers clashes, and armed robbery have assumed a worrisome dimension. According to the report of Amnesty International in year 2022, at least 6,907 people were killed in Nigeria, 6,157 people were abducted while at least 2,000 people were internally displaced. Security operatives are overwhelmed by insecurity challenges such as armed banditry, kidnapping, cattle rustling, farmers/ herders conflict, political unrest and inter-

communal conflict. Despite huge allocation to the security agencies, insecurity has been a threat to lives and property in Nigeria. Therefore, use of technology to assist security operatives in Nigeria required re-examination since existing researches on insecurity challenges have not sufficiently addressed the issue. To this end, this study is to appraise Ondo state government directive on installation of closed-circuit television camera (CCTV) using Owo Local government area, Ondo state, Nigeria as a case study

Research Questions

- i. What is the level of awareness on Ondo State government directive on installation of closed-circuit television camera (CCTV) in Owo local government area?
- ii. What is the level of compliance on Ondo state directive on installation of closed-circuit television camera (CCTV) in Owo local government area?
- iii. What is the extent to which the directive has curbed crimes and criminalities in Owo local government area?
- iv. What are the possible ways to fight crimes and criminalities in Owo local government area?

Objectives of the Study

- i. Examine the level of awareness on Ondo state government directive on installation of closed-circuit television camera (CCTV) in Owo Local Government Area.
- ii. Determine the level of compliance on Ondo State government directive on installation of closed –circuit television camera (CCTV) in Owo local government area.
- iii. Access the extent to which the directive has curbed crimes and criminalities in the local government area.
- iv. Recommend possible ways to fight crimes and criminalities in the Owo local government

Purpose of the study

The purpose of the study is to appraise Ondo state government directive on Installation of closed –circuit television camera (CCTV) with the view of offering recommendations that would help in reducing crimes and criminalities in Owo local government area.

2. LITERATURE AND CONCEPTUAL REVIEW

The section provides a conceptual definition of Insecurity, closed-circuit Television camera (CCTV) review of relevant and related literature, and comprised of theoretical framework.

Conceptual Definition

Insecurity

Insecurity has been referred to as the absence of safety, danger, uncertainty and lack of adequate protection. Ali (2013) defines insecurity as the state of fear or anxiety as a result of concrete or lack of protection. According to Abdullahi (2022) it refers to as lack of inadequate freedom from danger which stemmed into many other forms of insecurity such as economic and social insecurity. In another way, it is defined as the condition of being subjected to danger or threat of danger where danger is the condition of being capable to harm or injure (Adeola & Oluyemi, 2012)

Closed-circuit Television

According to Bayu and Muhammad (2017) closed circuit television camera is a device used to monitor and transmit video signals in a space to be forwarded to the monitor screen. Kumar and Svensson (2015) define closed-circuit television as a gadget that uses video cameras to transmit a signal to a specific place, on a limited set of monitors. It is the use of video cameras for capturing images for the purpose of viewing in predetermined monitors or television screens (Maxwell et al, 2018). Closed circuit Television (CCTV) is classified into CCTV analog; and CCTV Digital. While CCTV Analog works by transmitting continuous video streaming through coaxial cable, CCTV Digital used discrete video streaming via UTP cable. Its cameras are generally equipped with IP address often called IP (network) camera (Bayu & Mohammed, 2017)

Empirical Review

According to Onoja (2014) divergent approaches to the conceptualization of security in scholarly discourse can be categorized into two main approaches. The traditional approach that regards the state as referent (Buzan, 1991), and the second approach as humans beings (Kerr, 2010). The proponents of the first approach focus on the state and the external military dimension of security which was born out of the realities of European politics as a result of their engagement of the cold war (Onoja, 2014). The human being approach of security conceptualizes security as the responsibility of non-state actors and displaces the state as a major provider of security (Okonkwo et al, 2015). The proponents of this approach argue that security is beyond a military determination of threat but economic security of an individual. The root causes of insecurity are economic in nature. Security entails all measures designed to protect lives and assets of individuals, groups, and the country against violent occurrence (Ogunleye, et al, 2011). The notion of insecurity connotes different meaning such as; absences of safety; danger, uncertainty and absence of adequate protection. Ali (2013) defines insecurity as the state of fear or anxiety as a result of concrete or lack of protection. Abdullahi (2022) defines insecurity as lack or inadequate freedom from danger which stemmed into many other forms of insecurity such as economic and social insecurity. In the view of Achumba et al (2013) insecurity can be viewed from two angles. Firstly, insecurity is the state of being subjected to danger or threat of danger, where danger is the condition of being exposed to harm or injury. Secondly, insecurity is the state of being opined to risk or anxiety, where anxiety is an equivocal unpleasant emotion that is accomplished in expectant of some adversities. These definitions of insecurity by different Scholars highlight a key view that those affected by insecurity are also exposed to threats and dangers when they occur. Critically appraising Nigeria's security challenges, the state security apparatus needs to be overhauled and reconfigured with technology devices that will help in crime defection and prevention. By this, the state could be secured against threats which may include crime, organized violence, kidnapping, armed robbery and armed insurgency (El-Rufia, 2012)

Theoretical Framework

The study is anchored on the theoretical framework of Routine activity theory developed by Lawrence Cohen and Marcus Felson (1979). Routine activity theory took basic element time, place, an object and person to develop a "routine activities" theory of crime events. It posits that crime is likely to occur when they are convergence of three essential elements of crime. According to Cohen and Felson (1979), the three major categories of variables identified are; a motivated offender, a suitable target and absence of capable guidance. The motivated offender is a person who is motivated and has a capacity to commit a crime. A suitable target is a person or properties that may be threatened by an offender while the absence of a capable guardian implies someone who can intervene to stop or impede a crime. A guardian capable of preventing crime is one in whose presence the crime is not committed and whose absence makes it more probable (Felson, 1995). Situating the theory in the context of Ondo state government directive on the installation of closed-circuit television, the motivated offenders represent criminal elements that are willing to commit a crime and also have the capacity to do so. The suitable target represents soft targets that could be attacked by criminals and probably get away without being caught by security agents. Capable guardian in this context is not restricted to the police alone but anyone/thing who moves through an area or functions as a guard of person or property. In Nigeria, the police ability to combat criminalities has been limited by the amount or resources available to it (Adesina, 2012). Nigeria police is constitutionally empowered to maintain law and order (chapter 6. Part 3. S.214, the 1999 constitution) but lacks enough personnel to do so. The organization has shortage of well-trained intelligence gathering officers within its ranks. This has accounted for ineffective policing of the country, poor crime, detection and increase in crime and criminal activities in Nigeria (Yunusa & Usman, 2022) Therefore to assist security agencies in crime defection and prevention, many countries around the world has deployed the use of technology. In Nigeria, some states, private individuals and organizations have embraced the use of technology to complement the efforts of private security outfits employed to provide safety. The most commonly used technological device for crime defection and prevention in Nigeria is the Closed-circuit television camera (CCTV). According to Amanda et.al (2021) closed-circuit television has been keyed in crime investigation in recent times as a criminal can be easily identified, tracked and subsequently apprehended through the use of the device. It is effective in capturing of images and cost less in terms of men and logistics (Yau, 2019). The gadget could be the capable use to detect and prevent crime in public places. Routine activity theory, therefore, reveals the importance of closed-circuit television (CCTV) as a capable guardian whose presence could prevent crime but whose absence makes it more probable.

3. METHODOLOGY

Study Area

The study was carried out in Owo local government. Owo is a local government in Ondo state Nigeria. It has its administrative headquarters in the town of Owo. The local government has the following districts/towns under it; Igboroko, Ijebu, Iloro, Ehin-Ogbe, Ipele, Isaipen, Isuada, Ipenmen, Idashe, Obasofo, Uso, Amurin, and Emure-ile.

Population of the Study

The population of study consists of all inhabitants of Owo local government area. According to the National Population Commission (2006) the total population of Owo local government is put at 222,262.

Sample and Sample Technique

The study used purposive and multi-stage sampling technique to select participants for the study. In the first stage three (3) towns were randomly selected out of the ten (10) communities in the LG. The selected towns were Ipele, Emure-Ile and Owo. Then a total of two hundred (200) respondents were randomly selected in proportion of each town and a further six (6) were selected for the interview, making two hundred and six (206) to form sample size for the study.

Instrument of Data Collection.

Structured questionnaires were used to collect quantitative data from two (200) respondents selected for the study and in-depth interview (IDI) were used to collect qualitative data from six (6) purposively selected respondents. The responses generated from the use of structured questionnaires and in-depth interview formed primary data while secondary data were sourced from both published journals, newspapers, articles and internet.

Method of Data presentation and Analysis

The data collected for the study was presented and analyzed with the aid of frequency table and simple percentages. The qualitative data collected were analyzed using content analysis and italicized text of discussion.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1: Profile of Respondents

No	Demographic Information	Option	Frequency	Percent	Cum Percent
1	Gender	Male	77	40.1	40.1
		Female	115	59.9	100.0
		Total	192	100.0	
2	Ages Group	Below 30 years	67	34.9	34.9
		31-40 years	77	40.1	75.0
		41-50 years	16	8.3	83.3
		50 years Above	32	16.7	100.0
		Total	192	100.0	
3	Education Status	No formal Education	32	16.7	16.7
		Primary Education	67	34.9	51.6
		Secondary Education	77	40.1	91.7
		Tertiary Education	16	8.3	100.0
		Total	192	100.0	
4	Marital Status	Single	105	54.7	54.7
		Married	51	26.6	81.3
		Divorced	35	18.2	99.5
		Separated	1	.5	100.0
		Total	192	100.0	
5	Occupation of Respondent	Farmers	55	28.6	28.6
		Traders	54	28.1	56.8
		Civil Servants	45	23.4	80.2
		Artisan	06	3.1	83.3
		Students	32	16.7	100.0
		Total	162	100.0	

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

The table showed a well-balanced gender split with 59.9% women and 40.1% men. In terms of age, 34.9% fall below 30 years, 40.1% are between 31-40 years, 8.3% are between the ranges of 41-50 years and 16.7% are above 50 years. The table also showed that 16.7% of the respondents have no formal education, 34.9% of them were primary school holders, and 40.1% have secondary education while 8.3% have tertiary education. Also, 54.7% of the respondents were single compared to 26.6% of respondents who were married, 18.25 who were divorced and only 1% that was separated respectively. The table further revealed that 28.6% of respondents were farmers, 28.1% were traders, 23.4% were civil/public servants, 3.1% were artisans and 16.7% were students.

Analysis of the Responses from the Respondents

Question 1: What is the level of awareness on Ondo State government directive on installation of closed-circuit television camera (CCTV) in Owo local government area?

Table 2:

Rated Option (%)

S/N	Level of awareness on installation of CCTV Owo local government area	Yes	No	Not Sure	I don't know
1	Ondo State government directive on installation of CCTV camera is all over the news	36 (18.8%)	12 (6.3%)	54 (28.1%)	90 (46.9%)
2	Ondo state Radiovision Corporation (OSRC) creates an awareness, jingles and announcement on the directive	35 (18.2%)	16 (8.3%)	48 (25.0%)	93 (48.4%)
3	Government agencies distributed flyers to create awareness on the directive	50 (26.0%)	17 (8.9%)	55 (28.6%)	70 (36.5%)
4	Community/Opinion/Religious leaders are involved in creating awareness on the directive	72 (37.5%)	17 (8.9%)	48 (25.0%)	55 (28.6%)
5	Everybody in the state is aware of the directive on installation of CCTV camera by Ondo state government	24 (12.5%)	23 (12.0%)	45 (23.4%)	100 (52.1%)

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 2 presents data gathered from respondents on level of awareness on installation of closed-circuit television camera in Owo local government area. The result showed that 81.7% of the respondents said the awareness on the directive on installation of closed-circuit television camera was not over the news compared to 18.8% who said it was over the news. Also, 81.7% of the respondents said the state owned Radio vision corporation did not create awareness on the directive compared to 18.2% who think so. The result also revealed that 62.5% of the respondents said government did not involve community, opinion and religious leaders in creating awareness for the directive compared to 37.5% who think otherwise. Majority of the respondents 87.5% were not aware of the directive. This view is substantiated by one of the opinion leaders when he said:

The majority of people especially in the rural areas are not aware of the state government directive on installation of closed-circuit television camera. The awareness is very low and this is because government did not give the directive wide publicity as expected. Since the attack on St. Francis church, Owaluwa, I doubt whether any church or mosque has installed CCTY in their domains (IDI/Male, 53 years, Holder of bachelor degree)

Question 2: What is the level of compliance on Ondo state directive on installation of closed-circuit television in Owo local government area?

Table 3:

Rated Option (%)

S/N	What is the level of compliance on directive to install closed circuit television camera CCTV in Owo local government area	Yes	No	Not Sure	I don't know
1	Public institutions provide security cameras to monitor activities in their domains	34 (18.8%)	08 (4.2%)	64 (33.3%)	84 (43.8%)
2	All worship centres are installed with security surveillance gadgets	39 (20.3%)	05 (2.6%)	69 (35.9%)	79 (41.1%)
3	Hotels have functional security cameras to monitor people coming and going out of their premises	54 (28.1%)	09 (4.7%)	49 (25.5%)	80 (41.7%)

4	Public institutions and worship centres report their compliance on the directives to the government	51 (26.6%)	06 (3.1%)	51 (31.8%)	86 (38.5%)
5	Public institutions and worship centres have been covered with security cameras.	50 (26.0%)	05 (2.6%)	51 (26.6%)	86 (44.8%)

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 3 presents the data generated from respondents on the level of compliance with the state government directive on installation of closed-circuit television camera (CCTV). The result showed 77.1% of the respondents said public institutions in Owo local government did not provide security camera to monitor activities in their domains compared to 23% who think so. The result also revealed that 70.3% of the respondents did not think public institution and worship centres have reported their compliance on the directive to government compared to 29.7% who think so. Majority of the respondents 71.4% did not think public Institutions and worship centres have been covered with security cameras. This was validated in view of a community leader when she said:

Since Governor Akeredolu made the pronouncement that public institutions should install CCTV in their domains, only few had complied with the directive. Go to any public primary or secondary school whether you will find any CCTV there. I don't know why the level of compliance on the directive is low. Maybe it is because of the cost of the gadgets. I don't think many private schools can afford it (IDI/Female, 55 years, Holder of National Diploma).

Question 3: what is the extent to which the directive to install closed-circuit television camera has curbed crimes and criminalities in Owo local government area?

Table 4:

Rated Option (%)

S/N	What is the extent to which the directive has curbed crimes and criminalities in Owo local government area?	SA	A	D	SD
1	The installation of security cameras in public places and worship centres does not enhance crime reduction in Owo local government	49 (25.5%)	25 (13.0%)	48 (25.0%)	70 (36.5%)
2	Security cameras have enhanced better surveillance and monitoring of hot spots in Owo local government	42 (20.3%)	25 (13.0%)	43 (22.4%)	82 (42.7%)
3	Security agencies can prevent crime without the aid of closed-circle television (CCTV) camera	54 (21.9%)	09 (4.7%)	49 (25.5%)	80 (41.7%)
4	The technology has complemented security agents efforts in crime prevention in Owo local government	29 (15.1%)	29 (15.1%)	59 (30.7%)	75 (39.1%)
5	Security has improved based on the compliance on government directive on installation of closed-circuit camera television	34 (17.7%)	18 (9.4%)	47 (24.5%)	93 (48.4%)

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 4 presents data generated from respondents on extent to which the directive has curbed crimes and criminalities in Owo local government area. The result showed that 61.55 of the respondents did not agree that the installation of the technology will enhance crime reduction compared to 38.5% who think so. While 65.1% of the respondents agreed that the technology will not enhance better surveillance and monitoring of hot spots in Owo local government area, 33.3% think it will. Also, the result revealed that 26.3% of the respondents agreed that the gadget can complement efforts of security agents in crime prevention while 69.8% think otherwise. Majority of the respondents 72.9% did not believe that security has improved in Owo local government as a result of compliance on the directive to install closed –circuit television camera. An extraction of text of discussion throws more lights to the result. A youth leader said:

I don't think the technology will enhance or prevent crimes in the local government. This is because there is a lack of facility to support effective deployment of the technology. Our lack of maintenance culture is another issue that would hinder the technology. Also, I don't think security would improve because of CCTV because in place they have the technology; people still commit crimes (IDI/Male, 45 years, Holder of bachelor degree

Question 4: what are the possible ways to fight crimes and criminalities in Owo local government area?

Table 5: Rated Option (%)

S/N	What are the possible ways to fight against crimes and criminalities in Owo local government area?	SA	A	D	SD
1	Improve conditions of service for security agencies will guarantee crime prevention	75 (39.1%)	34 (17.7%)	36 (18.8%)	47 (24.5%)
2	Increase salaries and allowances for security agencies will improve their commitments to fight crime	63 (32.8%)	46 (24.0%)	36 (18.8%)	47 (24.5%)
3	Owo local government should pay special allowance to security agencies to increase their motivation to fight crime	82 (42.7%)	51 (26.6%)	20 (10.4%)	39 (20.3%)
4	Vigilantes and local hunters should be employed to assist police in crime prevention instead of closed-circuit television camera (CCTV)	54 (28.1%)	39 (20.3%)	44 (22.9%)	55 (28.6%)
5	Security agents should be stationed in all public institutions and worship centres in the local government	84 (43.8%)	38 (19.8%)	22 (11.5%)	48 (25.0%)

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 5 presents data generated from respondents on the possible ways to fight crimes and criminalities in Owo local government area. The result showed that improve conditions of service for security agencies will guarantee crime reduction with 56.8% of the respondents agreed on that compared to 43.4% who think otherwise. The result also revealed that 56.8% of the respondents agreed that increase salary and allowance will improve security agencies commitment to fight crimes compared to 43.3% who think otherwise. 51.5% of the r respondents did not agree that vigilantes and local hunters should be employed to assist police in crime prevention compared to 48.4% who believed so. However, majority of the respondents 63.6% agreed that security agents should be stationed in all public institutions and worship centres in Owo local government area. A former security Officer in his expression said:

The salary of police and other security agents is poor. There is an urgent need for the government to improve conditions of working for police Officer, recruit and train more personnel who should be armed with more sophisticated weapon to handle wave of criminalities in the society. Also, government should consider having community police to help close the gap in intelligence gathering effective policing at the grassroots (IDI/Male, 67 years, Holder of Higher National Diploma)

5. SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

The results of the field survey have showed that there is low level of awareness on Ondo state government directive on installation of closed-circuit television camera (CCTV). This was attributed to the inefficiency of government owned media houses and platforms to embark on aggressive and wide publicity. Also, the level of compliance on the directive was poor. The directive was a government executive order and not a law. This probably informed lack of political will by government and security agencies to enforce the directive. Also, there is no empirical fact to show that the directive has reduced crimes I the study area. Despite effort of few public institutions and worship centres of installing closed-circuit television camera in their premises, crimes and criminalities still persist in the local government. The survey found out that most respondents canvassed for better conditions of service for security agencies in their fight against crimes and criminalities in Owo local government area.

6. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The impact of insecurity on lives and properties in Ondo state is significant and concerning. The state has experienced various forms of insecurity including terrorist attacks, armed robbery, kidnapping, cult-related killings, etc. these incidents have resulted in loss of lives, ,destruction of properties, displacement of residents, and a general sense of fear which has negative implications for the social fabric of the state. Additionally, destruction of properties due to insecurity has exacerbated economic challenges faced by individual and businesses in the state. The study revealed that effort of Ondo state government in protecting lives and properties through the installation of closed-circuit television camera has received

little awareness, low level of compliance and crimes and criminalities still persist in the state. Based on the findings and conclusion of this study, the following recommendations were made in line with the objectives of the study;

1. The state government should create public awareness and collaboration with civil societies and non-governmental organisations on the directive. Publicity is key in any government policies and programmes that borders on implementation of laws, executive orders directives, etc. This can be achieved by collaborating with civil organisations to help drive the awareness.
2. To have the political will to enforce the directive and involve law enforcement agencies, there is a need for the Ondo state House of Assembly to pass the directive into law with penalties for those who refuse to comply with such law. This will give security operatives the legal backing to enforce it.
3. More security personnel should be employed and professionally trained in intelligence gathering. Without adequate training, security would not be able to leverage on technology such as the use of surveillance cameras to identify hotspots and target criminal networks.
4. The conditions of service for security agencies should be reviewed and improved. The commitment to fight crimes and criminalities can only be assured when security agents are adequately compensated for risking their lives for the protection of others.
5. Improve infrastructure and lighting. Enhancing the physical infrastructures, particularly in vulnerable areas can help deter criminal activities. Installing street lights in strategic locations, improving road network, and securing public spaces can make it more challenging for criminals to operate covertly and escape unnoticed.
6. Promote youth empowerment and employment. Addressing the underlying socio-economic factors that contribute to crimes and criminalities is very crucial. Therefore, government should implement programmes that provide skill training, educating and employment opportunities for young people so as to help reduce their vulnerability to involve and engage in criminal activities.
7. Further studies are recommended on the use of technology such as closed-circuit camera (CCTV) in crime detection and prevention.

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